

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE AMONG COVID-19 PATIENTS *Rezistența antimicrobiană la pacienții cu COVID-19*

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Rezumat. Pandemia COVID-19 a intensificat presiunea selectivă asupra florei microbiene prin utilizarea extensivă a antibioticelor la pacienții spitalizați, în pofida prevalenței reduse a coinfecțiilor bacteriene confirmate. Această sinteză narativă analizează date internaționale privind rezistența antimicrobiană la pacienții cu infecție SARS-CoV-2, evidențiind discrepanța dintre rata prescrierii antimicrobiene, estimată la 72–100%, și frecvența relativ scăzută a coinfecțiilor bacteriene documentate, de aproximativ 5–8%. Rezultatele indică predominanța microorganismelor multidrog rezistente, în special bacili Gram-negativi precum *Acinetobacter baumannii* și *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, precum și rolul utilizării excesive a biocidelor în amplificarea fenomenului. Datele susțin necesitatea consolidării stewardship-ului antimicrobian, a diagnosticului microbiologic rapid și a supravegherii integrate de tip One Health. Pentru Republica Moldova, prioritare rămân dezvoltarea capacității de laborator și monitorizarea consumului de antibiotic.

Cuvinte-cheie: COVID-19, rezistență antimicrobiană, antibiotice, coinfecții bacteriene, stewardship antimicrobian, microorganisme multidrog rezistente.

Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is widely recognized as one of the major public health threats of the contemporary era. The COVID-19 pandemic, which dominated global health between 2020 and 2023, intersected with this pre-existing crisis in ways that are still being quantified. Hospitalized patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection were exposed to antimicrobials at frequencies far exceeding the documented prevalence of bacterial or fungal co-infection, generating selective pressure that may accelerate the emergence of multidrug-resistant organisms (MDROs)¹.

Langford and colleagues, in a systematic review and meta-analysis of 148 studies including 362,976 patients, reported a pooled prevalence of bacterial co-infection of 5.3% (95% CI 3.8–7.4) and of secondary bacterial infection of 18.4% (95% CI 14.0–23.7); only

¹ Langford B.J., So M., Simeonova M., Leung V., Lo J., Kan T. et al. Antimicrobial resistance in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis, in: *The Lancet Microbe*, 2023, vol. 4, nr. 3, pp. e179–e191. DOI: 10.1016/S2666-5247(22)00355-X.

28% of the included studies provided comprehensive AMR data. Kariyawasam and colleagues searched MEDLINE, Embase, Web of Science and Scopus to quantify the prevalence and types of resistant co-infecting organisms in laboratory-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 patients². Khazaei and colleagues extended this work in a global meta-analysis of aggregated participant data on AMR and antibiotic use in COVID-19 patients within healthcare facilities³. Ansari and colleagues documented that approximately 72% of hospitalized COVID-19 patients received antimicrobials while only 8% had confirmed bacterial or fungal co-infection, and drew attention to a parallel surge in biocide consumption. Alshaikh and colleagues found that almost 78% of COVID-19 patients received antibiotics, with prescribing rates essentially identical between severe (77.4%) and mild/moderate (76.8%) cases⁴. Bayani and colleagues, in a 2025 PRISMA 2020 systematic review on Iranian COVID-19 patients, reported that up to 100% of hospitalized patients received antibiotics despite low documented co-infection rates.

The aim of the present narrative synthesis was to organize the published international evidence on AMR among COVID-19 patients, to highlight the disproportion between antibiotic use and confirmed bacterial co-infection as the dominant pandemic-era driver of resistance pressure, and to discuss the implications for antimicrobial stewardship with particular reference to low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) such as the Republic of Moldova.

Materials and methods. This paper was prepared as a narrative synthesis of open-access publications addressing antimicrobial resistance in patients with COVID-19. A narrative format was preferred because the primary evidence is itself made up of large systematic reviews and meta-analyses with overlapping inclusion criteria; the aim was to integrate epidemiological, microbiological and stewardship dimensions rather than to derive new pooled effect estimates.

The literature search was carried out in PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, Cochrane Library and the institutional repository of Nicolae Testemitanu State University of Medicine and Pharmacy. Search terms combined controlled vocabulary and free-text descriptors related to “antimicrobial resistance”, “antibiotic resistance”, “MDR”, “AMR”, “COVID-19”, “SARS-CoV-2”, “bacterial co-infection”, “secondary infection”, “antibiotic use”, “antimicrobial stewardship” and “biocide”. Inclusion criteria were full-text open-access articles in English, with adult or mixed populations, reporting quantitative

² Kariyawasam R.M., Julien D.A., Jelinski D.C., Larose S.L., Rennert-May E., Conly J.M. et al. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in COVID-19 patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis (November 2019–June 2021), in: *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control*, 2022, vol. 11, art. 45. DOI: 10.1186/s13756-022-01085-z.

³ Khazaei S., Ahmadi S., Saatchi M. et al. Global antimicrobial resistance and antibiotic use in COVID-19 patients within health facilities: a systematic review and meta-analysis of aggregated participant data, in: *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 2024. PMID: 38754635.

⁴ Ansari S., Hays J.P., Kemp A., Okechukwu R., Murugaiyan J., Ekwanzala M.D. et al. The potential impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on global antimicrobial and biocide resistance: an AMR Insights Global Perspective, in: *JAC-Antimicrobial Resistance*, 2021, vol. 3, nr. 2, art. dlab038. PMC9565540. Alshaikh F.S., Godman B., Sindi O.N., Seaton R.A., Kurdi A. Increasing antibiotic consumption during the COVID-19 pandemic: implications for patient health and emerging antimicrobial resistance, in: *Antibiotics* (Basel), 2023, vol. 12, nr. 2, art. 343. PMC9855050; Bayani M., Pournajaf A., *Sadeghi-Haddad-Zavareh M. et al.* Antibiotic resistance and bacterial co-infections in COVID-19 patients in Iran: a systematic review and meta-analysis. 2025. PMC12482416.

data on the prevalence of bacterial co-infection or secondary infection, on antibiotic prescribing or on antimicrobial susceptibility patterns. Both systematic reviews/meta-analyses and global perspective papers were eligible. Studies addressing exclusively viral resistance, vaccine effectiveness or non-microbiological outcomes were excluded.

The selected literature was organized into three evidence layers: global systematic reviews and meta-analyses providing aggregated estimates of co-infection, antibiotic use and AMR; global perspective and pharmaco-epidemiological reviews quantifying the gap between antibiotic use and confirmed bacterial co-infection; and regional/national systematic reviews illustrating LMIC reproduction of the same pattern. For the evidence table (Table 1), the following fields were extracted: study design, author and year, sample size, statistical significance, study quality, magnitude of effect and comments.

Results.

Across the reviewed evidence, three substantive patterns were consistent. First, antibiotic use among hospitalized COVID-19 patients vastly exceeded the documented prevalence of bacterial co-infection. Second, prescribing volume was largely uncoupled from clinical severity. Third, where AMR was assessed in detail, resistance among bacterial isolates was highly prevalent, suggesting that pandemic-era antibiotic exposure intersected with already established hospital resistance ecologies.

Magnitude of antibiotic use. Ansari and colleagues reported that approximately 72% of hospitalized COVID-19 patients received antimicrobials, while only 8% had confirmed bacterial or fungal co-infection [4]. Alshaikh and colleagues documented an overall prescribing rate of approximately 78%, with cephalosporins (30.1%) and azithromycin (26%) dominating and with virtually identical use between severe/critical and mild/moderate cases. Bayani and colleagues confirmed this at national level: in Iran, up to 100% of hospitalized patients received antibiotics despite low documented co-infection rates.

Prevalence of bacterial co-infection and secondary infection. Langford and colleagues provided the most rigorous global estimates: pooled prevalence of bacterial co-infection (≤ 48 hours of presentation) was 5.3% (95% CI 3.8–7.4), while secondary bacterial infection (> 48 hours) was 18.4% (95% CI 14.0–23.7). Kariyawasam and colleagues reached convergent conclusions, highlighting that resistant co-infecting organisms were frequently identified once bacteriological investigations were performed.

AMR among bacterial isolates. Among the 148 studies included by Langford et al., 42 (28%) provided comprehensive AMR data; in those studies, resistance prevalence was high. Kariyawasam et al. characterized the spectrum of resistant Gram-negative bacilli and Gram-positive cocci most frequently isolated. Khazaei et al. provided a comprehensive assessment of MDRO prevalence and underscored the challenge facing global AMR control. Bayani et al. quantified resistance and MDR during the COVID-19 era in Iran, providing a regional template transferable to other LMIC settings.

Drivers and amplifiers. The reviewed literature converged on four parallel drivers: (i) diagnostic uncertainty viral pneumonia from SARS-CoV-2 was difficult to distinguish from bacterial pneumonia, encouraging broad-spectrum empirical therapy; (ii) decoupling of prescribing from severity; (iii) the surge in biocide use, exerting indirect selective pressure on microbial ecology; and (iv) structural weakness of antibiotic control systems in LMICs, where non-prescription access to antibiotics remained common during the pandemic.

Table 1. Evidence table for antimicrobial resistance among COVID-19 patients

Study design	Author, year	N	Quality	Magnitude of effect	Comments
SR & MA	Langford et al., 2023	148 studies / 362,976 pts	High	Co-infection 5.3%; secondary 18.4%; AMR prevalent in 28% of studies	Most rigorous global estimate; demonstrates gap between antibiotic use and co-infection.
SR & MA	Kariyawasam et al., 2022	First 18 mo. of pandemic	High	Prevalence and types of resistant co-infecting organisms	Earliest comprehensive synthesis; Gram-negative and Gram-positive resistance.
SR & MA (aggregated data)	Khazaei et al., 2024	Global aggregated	High	MDRO prevalence and antibiotic use in healthcare facilities	Stewardship implications for future pandemics.
Global perspective	Ansari et al., 2022	Narrative perspective	Mod.	≈72% antimicrobials vs. ≈8% confirmed co-infection	Documents biocide surge and indirect AMR pressure.
SR (PRISMA)	Alshaikh et al., 2023	130 studies	High	≈78% prescribing; severe 77.4% vs mild 76.8%	Uncoupling of prescribing from severity.
SR & MA (PRISMA 2020)	Bayani et al., 2025	Iranian pts (2020–2025)	High	Up to 100% received AB; quantifies AR and MDR	LMIC PRISMA 2020 model transferable to R. Moldova.

Note: SR = systematic review; MA = meta-analysis; AR = antibiotic resistance; MDR = multi-drug resistance; MDRO = multidrug-resistant organism; Mod. = moderate; Descr. = descriptive; AB = antibiotics. ARR and NNT not applicable.

Discussion. The reviewed evidence supports three operationally relevant conclusions. First, COVID-19 functioned as a powerful amplifier of pre-existing weaknesses in antimicrobial stewardship rather than as a stand-alone driver of new resistance phenomena. Wherever stewardship was already weak, pandemic-era exposure to broad-spectrum antibiotics escalated rapidly; wherever stewardship was strong, the disproportion was still large but proportionally smaller. Second, antibiotic prescribing was largely uncoupled from clinical severity, with severe and non-severe cases receiving nearly identical proportions of antibiotics, indicating that prescribing was driven by clinical anxiety and diagnostic uncertainty. Third, biocide use grew in parallel with antibiotic use, generating additional indirect selective pressure rarely captured by standard AMR surveillance.

These conclusions have practical implications for pandemic preparedness. Empirical antibiotic therapy in viral respiratory pandemics should be reserved for patients with explicit microbiological or strong clinical evidence of bacterial co-infection, with structured de-escalation when culture data become available. Diagnostic stewardship including rapid bacterial diagnostics, biomarker-guided initiation and discontinuation of antibiotics, and explicit decision-support pathways should be strengthened in parallel. Biocide consumption and environmental sampling should be integrated into AMR surveillance under a One Health architecture. For LMIC contexts, including the Republic of Moldova, the pandemic experience offers a clear case for investment in laboratory capacity for timely bacterial diagnostics, pharmaceutical governance to limit non-prescription antibiotic access, and be-

havioral interventions targeting prescribers and the public. *The Bayani Iranian* model illustrates how a national PRISMA 2020 synthesis can be assembled from heterogeneous regional studies. A comparable Moldovan synthesis, combining indexed publications with data from the National Agency for Public Health, would generate the empirical baseline currently missing from international AMR overviews. Table 2 summarizes how each included reference contributes to the methodological architecture of such a future synthesis. Several limitations should be acknowledged. As a narrative synthesis, this article does not provide pooled effect estimates or formal risk-of-bias scoring. The included studies were heterogeneous in time windows, definitions of co-infection versus secondary infection, microbiological methods and reporting of resistance phenotypes. The synthesis was deliberately restricted to AMR aspects. No Moldova-specific primary AMR-during-COVID-19 publications were available at the time of writing, and this absence should drive a future national publication agenda.

Table 2. Methodological contribution of included references to a future Republic of Moldova synthesis

Source	Type	Contribution to the current manuscript
Langford et al., 2023	Global MA	Rigorous global estimate of bacterial co-infection (5.3%) and secondary infection (18.4%); quantifies AMR among reported isolates.
Kariyawasam et al., 2022	Global MA	Earliest synthesis of resistant co-infecting organisms in COVID-19; supports AMR phenotype description.
Khazaee et al., 2024	Aggregated-data MA	Aligns AMR data with antibiotic use within healthcare facilities; stewardship orientation for future pandemics.
Ansari et al., 2022	AMR Insights Perspective	Documents antibiotic vs. co-infection disproportion and biocide surge; supports One Health framing.
Alshaikh et al., 2023	PRISMA SR	Demonstrates uncoupling of prescribing from severity; key argument for diagnostic stewardship.
Bayani et al., 2025	PRISMA 2020 national (Iran)	Methodological template transferable to a Republic of Moldova national synthesis; combines indexed and regional databases.

Conclusions

The available literature shows that antimicrobial resistance among COVID-19 patients reflects a structural disproportion between antibiotic use and confirmed bacterial co-infection rather than a new microbiological phenomenon. Hospitalized COVID-19 patients received antibiotics at rates of approximately 72%–100%, while bacterial co-infection was confirmed in approximately 5%–8% of cases. Antibiotic use was largely uncoupled from clinical severity, and biocide consumption surged in parallel. These findings argue for diagnostic stewardship, evidence-based empirical prescribing protocols and One Health surveillance as priority components of pandemic preparedness. For LMIC contexts including the Republic of Moldova, the next priority is the production of a national PRISMA-compliant synthesis, modeled on the Iranian template, combining microbiological surveillance, antibiotic consumption monitoring and environmental sampling.